

A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW OF NATIONAL MATERNAL AND CHILD HEALTH PROGRAMMES IN INDIA**C. H. Samarth*¹, Kulkarni V. Pratibha²**¹PG Scholar, Dept. of Kriya Shareera, Shri Dharmasthala Manjunatheshwra College of Ayurveda and Hospital, Hassan.²Professor and Head Dept. of Kriya Shareera, Shri Dharmasthala Manjunatheshwra College of Ayurveda and Hospital, Hassan.**How to cite this Article:** C. H. Samarth*¹, Kulkarni V. Pratibha² (2026). A Comprehensive Review Of National Maternal And Child Health Programmes In India. World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research, 12(1), 469–471. This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

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ABSTRACT

Child health programs in India have played a crucial role in improving infant, child, and maternal mortality rates. Ensuring child health through programs has thus gained momentum in India. The present paper aims at discussing in detail all prominent programs in India, including those for mother and child health, communicable & non-communicable diseases, nutrition deficiency, and reproductive health. Various prominent programs, including MCI or Maternal & Child Health Program, Integrated Child Development Services, Child Survival & Safe Motherhood Program, Reproductive & Child Health Program, have programs in their agendas which emphasize improving antenatal care, delivery care, neonatal care, & adolescent health. Other programs, including Universal Immunization Program, National Vector Borne Disease Control Program, & Mid Day Meal Scheme, have played a significant role in improving child health. The present paper focuses on how these programs, working in collaboration, have played a significant role in improving child health. Therefore, it can thus be assumed that increased child health programs working in collaboration have played a crucial role in improving child health.

KEYWORDS: The present paper focuses on how these programs, working in collaboration, have played a significant role in improving child health.

INTRODUCTION

Child health continues to be one of the biggest concerns within India because of the burden of infant deaths, malnutrition, and diseases that are preventable. In an effort to address these concerns, various programs that seek to control, prevent, and eradicate diseases that are considered significant causes of morbidity and mortality related to children have been rolled out by the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare and Central Health Council. These programs cover maternal and child care, nutrition, development, communicable and non-communicable diseases, as well as reproductive health.

The National Rural Health Mission (NRHM) has improved primary health care services, particularly in rural areas. Various initiatives, which are maternal and child-oriented, have been initiated through this mission, like the programme on “Maternal and Child Health” (MCH), which concentrates on antenatal care, safe

motherhood, immunization, and adolescent health. The “Integrated Child Development Services (ICDS)” Scheme relates to education, health, and Nutrition of children between 0-6 years.

Emphasis of the Child Survival and Safe Motherhood (CSSM) Programme: Reduction of maternal and child mortality. Emphasis of the Reproductive and Child Health (RCH) Programme: Reproductive regulation, maternal health, and adolescent health.

Additionally, the national programs like those that address the communicable diseases of TB, diarrheal diseases, acute respiratory infections, along with nutritional deficiencies such as anemia, iodine-deficiency disorders, and malnutrition, also have a remarkably positive effect on the health status of children. This suggests a very holistic approach towards dealing with the health and development of children in the Indian

population.

METHODS

The conceptual study was conducted by observing analysing the textual data gathered from classical textbooks, Journals, Published research articles in PubMed google scholar, and web search.

RIVIEW OF LITERATURE

This review was developed by systematically examining major national programmes related to maternal and child health in India. The material consisted of structured descriptions of each programme, including their objectives, service components, and operational strategies. The review focuses on describing how these programmes are designed, implemented, and coordinated to improve child health outcomes.

Methodological Approach

- Each programme was reviewed in terms of.
- Objectives and target population.
- Mechanisms for service delivery: MPHWs, ANMs, ASHAs, Anganwadi workers.
- Intersectoral coordination across health, nutrition, and education departments
- As seen earlier, Preventive and promotive components include influences that bear on children's well-being.

The various programmes were then synthesized in an effort to understand their collective role in improving maternal and child health in India.^[1]

1. Integrated Child Development Services (ICDS) Scheme

The ICDS scheme was reviewed for holistic child development. The different components examined were supplementary nutrition, preschool education, growth monitoring, health checkups, and referral services.

Anganwadi Centres, as service-delivery institutions, and coordination at various levels with health workers- the methodological review-were all part of the review process.^[2]

2. Maternal and Child Health Programme (MCH)

The framework of the MCH program was assessed for its focus on antenatal care, identification of high risk pregnancies, screening for anemia, anti-tetanus injection, and nutrition support. Care was taken to note the role of multipurpose health workers, as well as the concept of care continuum from pregnancy to early childhood.^[3]

3. Child Survival and Safe Motherhood Programme (CSSM)

CSSM Programme was included to evaluate the strategies regarding the safe delivery, newborn care, and early risk assessment of the newborns. Materials regarding the antenatal care, emergency obstetric care,

and better referrals were reviewed.^[4]

4. Reproductive & Child Health Programme (RCH)

RCH was assessed for its comprehensiveness with regard to fertility regulation, maternal health, reproductive health, and care of adolescents. The approach was designed with emphasis on the understanding of how the intervention combines decentralized planning outputs with demand-based services and enhanced facilities such as FRUs and PHCs.^[5]

5. National Communicable Disease Control Programmes

The programs reviewed included Universal Immunization Programme, Diarrheal Disease Control Programme, Acute Respiratory Infection Control Programme, Revised National Tuberculosis Control Programme^[6], Leprosy Eradication Programme, and Vector-Borne Disease Control Programme.^[7] The approach taken looked at how these programs contribute to reducing diseases among children through vaccination, creating awareness, and treating diseases early. According to several authors, including.^[8]

6. National Nutrition-Related Programs

Nutrition programs including Special Nutrition Program^[9], Mid-Day Meal Scheme, Anemia Prophylaxis Program, and National Iodine Deficiency Disorders Control Program were analyzed for their prevention of nutritional programs and methods in tackling micronutrient deficiencies in their programs.^[10,11]

7. National Non-Communicable Disease and Welfare Programmes

Thereafter, programmes such as the National School Health Programme, National Mental Health Programme, National Cancer Control Programme, and National Diabetes Programme were included to understand their relevance in early detection, school-based health education, and long-term disease prevention.^[12,13,14]

DISCUSSION

India's national programs for child health as been said to provide a broad, multi-level approach for enhancing child health. The Maternal and Child Health Program: The MCH Program provides, among other things, the corner stone of antenatal, intranatal, and postnatal care, thus tackling key factors for maternal and child mortality. The ICDS Program: It has a robust nutrition component with supplies of supplementary nutrition for preschool children.

The CSSM programme makes a significant contribution to safe delivery and survival of newborns by improving emergency obstetric care and referral processes. Another important programme is RCH, which emphasizes the continuity of care with respect to reproductive health, adolescents, and mothers, including related processes like RH, ARC, and MMR.

Immunization is considered one of the most successful interventions in the health sector still in practice today. The Universal Immunization Programme (UIP) shields children against serious vaccine-preventable diseases and is the cornerstone of control of communicable diseases in India. Vector control for diseases, control of tuberculosis, and diarrhea management programs further contribute to lowering the burden of morbidity in infants and children.

Nutritional interventions, including the Mid-Day Meal Scheme, are known to promote regular school attendance, alleviate hunger, and enhance growth. Interventions aimed at addressing micronutrient disorders, including Anemia Prophylaxis and Iodine Deficiency Disorder Control, are of paramount importance in terms of cognitive and physical growth.

Taken together, these interventions illustrate the value of a health, nutrition, and education response. Ongoing strengthening of monitoring, engagement, and capacity-building efforts are needed to ensure continued progress in child health outcomes.

CONCLUSION

The national programs designed to benefit maternal and child health in India, together, offer a holistic approach to public health aimed at ensuring improved survival, increased development, and decreased preventable morbidity among children. Several programs, including the “Maternal and Child Health Program (MCH),” help provide a solid foundation by ensuring antenatal care, safe delivery, early neonatal care, and consistent health surveillance. Programs initiated by the Indian government, through the help of grass-root workers, help extend these benefits to remote areas, thus decreasing maternal and infant deaths.

Another important area is covered by the Integrated Child Development Services (ICDS), which deals with the nutrition and mental and physical growth of young children. It is an important programme in the sense that it helps prevent malnutrition. Other programmes that are supplementary in nature include Child Survival and Safe Motherhood (CSSM) and Reproductive and Child Health (RCH). These programs provide the basic health care of mothers and adolescents. They include the identification and treatment of risks and referral services.

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